

MANAGEMENT OF MIDDLE MESIAL CANAL IN MANDIBULAR SECOND MOLAR – A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

The primary goal of endodontic therapy is to obtain a three-dimensional obturation of the root canal space after adequately cleaning and shaping the root canal space to eliminate tissue debris, microorganisms, and their byproducts. Clinicians frequently encounter anatomical variations in endodontic practice in day-to-day life, which must be properly addressed. Failure to identify and treat all the canals is a major cause of therapy failure. This case report details a left mandibular second permanent molar requiring root canal treatment, which was found to have three separate canals in the mesial root. On clinical examination, diagnosis of symptomatic irreversible pulpitis with symptomatic apical periodontitis was made and nonsurgical root canal treatment was planned. Initially, two mesial and one distal canal were located. On careful examination of the groove between the mesiobuccal and mesiolingual canal orifices, the middle mesial canal orifice was identified and the canal subsequently negotiated. This rare anatomical configuration highlights the importance for clinicians to be vigilant and anticipate such variations, utilizing appropriate diagnostic techniques both before and during treatment.

INTRODUCTION

The goal of root canal therapy is to eliminate all irritants from the root canal system, including necrotic pulp tissue, microorganisms, and their byproducts. A thorough understanding of pulp canal anatomy is essential for effectively cleaning and shaping the root canal system. Mandibular molars are the most commonly treated teeth in endodontics.¹ The mesial root of a mandibular molar commonly presents a mesiobuccal (MB) and a mesiolingual (ML) canal, while the distal root more often contains one canal rather than two. A narrow connection, known as the isthmus, often containing pulp tissue, exists between the two mesial or distal canals. This isthmus can give rise to anatomical variations such as middle canals.²

Barker et al.² and Vertucci and Williams³ were the first researchers to demonstrate the presence of an extra and independent canal in the mesial root of mandibular molars.

Later, Martinez-Berna and Badanelli⁴ also reported a middle canal in the distal root. Since then, numerous researchers have documented the presence of middle canals in both the mesial and distal roots of mandibular molars.

While this middle canal has been named as

- Intermediate canal, ⁵
- Mesio-central canal, ⁶
- Third mesial canal, ⁷
- Accessory mesial canal, ⁸ and
- Middle mesial canal ^{9,10}

However, the term middle mesial canal/middle distal canal (MDC) has found its common usage.

A micro-CT study by Harris et al ¹¹ reported that 36% of mandibular first molars have more than two canals in the mesial root. Many authors have proposed that troughing in the floor of the pulp chamber and using a dental operating microscope are effective and safe methods for examining the mesial root for the potential presence of a middle mesial (MM) canal. ^{10,12} In addition to the MM canal, very few cases have reported a third canal located in the distal root. The purpose of this article is to report the successful treatment of mandibular first molar with three mesial and one distal canal.

CASE REPORT

A 30-year-old male patient reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry And Endodontics with decayed tooth and associated pain over his left mandibular region. Intraoral examination revealed class I pit and fissure carious lesion in 37. The tooth exhibited no mobility, was mildly tender to percussion, and gave a negative response to heat test and a mild reaction to an electric pulp tester.

PRE-OPERATIVE PHOTOGRAPH

PRE-OPERATIVE RADIOGRAPH

The preoperative diagnostic radiograph of 37 revealed a widening of the apical periodontal ligament space and loss of lamina dura and ill-defined radiolucency seen with the mesial and distal root of 37. Radiolucency involving furcation area seen with 37. A diagnosis of symptomatic irreversible pulpitis with symptomatic apical periodontitis was made. A CBCT was done which revealed three canals in mesial root.

LONGITUDINAL SECTION

AXIAL SECTION

- After administration of local anesthesia and rubber dam isolation, the carious lesion was removed and an adequate endodontic access prepared.
- Inspection of the pulp chamber floor showed orifices corresponding to mesiobuccal, mesiolingual, and distal canals.
- On careful examination of the groove between the mesiobuccal and mesiolingual canal orifices, the middle mesial canal orifice was identified and the canal was subsequently negotiated.
- The working lengths were established with an electronic apex locator (Dentsply X-Smart Endomotor), and size 10 K files of 21 mm length (Mani, Inc, Japan) were used to confirm the three canals in the mesial root radiographically.
- The working length measurement radiograph showed middle mesial canals which was connecting to mesiobuccal canals with no separate apical foramen or root.

ACCESS CAVITY SHOWING 3
MESIAL CANALSWORKING LENGTH
RADIOGRAPH

- Recapitulation was done with no 15 K file before moving to another file along with copious irrigation with 5.2% sodium hypochlorite (Prime Dental Products, India), 17% EDTA gel (Prime Dental Products, India) was used for lubricating the canals & saline used as final irrigant.
- Final preparation was carried out using Neo Endo file (Orikam Healthcare, India) up to 6% taper 20 size of the instrument.
- The canals after preparation were finally flushed with sterile saline, dried with sterile paper points, and a calcium hydroxide dressing was given.
- At the subsequent visit after a week, the tooth was asymptomatic and was obturated with gutta percha cones using Dia-Proseal sealer (DiaDent Group International).
- The patient experienced no postoperative sequelae and an appropriate post-endodontic restoration was performed in a subsequent appointment to ensure an adequate coronal seal.

MASTER CONE
RADIOGRAPH

OBTURATION
RADIOGRAPH

DISCUSSION

Detecting additional canals requires a thorough understanding of root canal morphology and its common variations. Careful examination of the pulpal floor, selective troughing, and enhanced visualization using a dental operating microscope are essential for identifying additional canals in a mandibular first molar.^{10,12} Martins *et al.* proposed that the third mesial canal is not an accessory canal but rather a sequela connected to the isthmus.¹³ Some research articles report that the third canal is located equidistant from both main canals, while others suggest it is closer to one of the main canals.¹⁴ Sherwani *et al.*¹⁵ observed that MMC is more prevalent in mandibular first molars with two distal canals (45.4%) compared to those with one distal canal (13.7%). In contrast, Nosrat *et al.*¹² found no significant association between the presence of an MMC and the presence of separate distal canals.

The clinician should carefully examine the pulp chamber floor to identify potential canal orifices. The anatomy of the pulp chamber floor and walls serves as a guide to determining root canal morphology. Krasner and Rankow¹⁶ made a rational approach to study the relationship between the pulp chamber and the clinical crown and pulp chamber floor. Their observations, presented as laws, are valuable tools for clinicians searching for elusive canals. Failure to identify extra canals and recognize unusual canal configurations is one of the most common reasons for the failure of endodontic therapy.¹⁷

In this case, shallow troughing, no more than 2 mm deep, was performed using a long shank bur to remove the dentin protuberance covering the developmental groove or isthmus and to explore the canal orifice within it. The advantage of using a bur instead of an ultrasonic tip is that it creates larger debris, which can be easily removed by irrigation. Magnification with loupes or a microscope enhances visibility, aiding in the detection of small, hidden canals.¹⁸

Wallance and Baugh⁶ reported a case of MM canal in the mandibular first molar, where MM canal originated as a separate orifice, but joined in the apical third of the canal. Izaz *et al.*¹⁹ reported a case of MD canal that joined the main canal in the apical third. However, in this case, middle mesial canals was connecting to mesiobuccal canals with no separate apical foramen or root. The present report confirms that the third canal in the mesial root of mandibular second molar does occur and must be sought along the line between the two mesial canals after accessing the pulp chamber and any cervical stenosis in this zone that might cover the opening of the canals, using burs or ultrasonic tips.²⁰⁻²²

CONCLUSION

The ability to disinfect the root canal system is of paramount importance in endodontic treatment. Achieving a completely sterile environment is often challenging due to the presence of additional canals, lateral canals, ramifications, and intracanal connections. Detecting and instrumenting these additional canals is crucial to preventing treatment failure. In addition to using various diagnostic tools, operator experience plays a key role in identifying these aberrant canals. Clinicians should be aware of the incidence of such variations in mandibular second molars and perform a preoperative radiological assessment from different angles, ensure proper access preparation, and thoroughly examine the pulp

chamber to locate and debride all canals. An accurate clinical evaluation of root canal number and morphology in mandibular second molars should utilize various diagnostic methodologies, including magnification and illumination, to ensure the long-term success of endodontic therapy. Careful interpretation of symptoms, combined with a thorough examination of the access cavity under a dental operating microscope, is essential which significantly decreases the chance of missing these hidden anatomies.

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